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AVTOBIOGRAFIK ASARLARNING BADIY TALQINI

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada avtobiografik asarlarning badiiy talqini tahlil qilinadi, bolalik tajribalari, bosh qahramonlarning rivojlanib borishi Maksim Gorkiy, Chingiz Aytmatov asarlari orqali yoritib beriladi. Shuningdek, ishda qahramonlarning o'z hayotiga munosabatlari bayon etiladi. Bolalik xotiralarini yetkazishda muallifning texnikalarini ko'rsatish uchun ba'zi asosiy parchalar keltirilgan. Bundan tashqari, maqolada qahramonning jamiyatda mustaqil shaxs sifatida shakllanishi ko'rsatiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: qahramon, qiyinchiliklarga bardosh bermoq, mavzu, muallif, bosh qahramon.

Аннотация: В статье исследуется художественная интерпретация автобиографических произведений, с акцентом на изображение детских переживаний, развитие характера и психологический рост в литературе Максима Горького, Чингиза Айтматова. В работе определяется, как семейные отношения влияют на жизнь главных героев. Приводятся ключевые фрагменты, иллюстрирующие приемы авторов в передаче детских воспоминаний. Кроме того, анализируется стремление героя стать независимой личностью в обществе.

Ключевые слова: персонаж, преодоление трудностей, тема, автор, главный герой.

Abstract: The article explores the artistic interpretation of autobiographical works, focusing on the depiction of childhood experiences, character development, and psychological growth in the literature of Maxim Gorky, Chingiz Aytmatov. The study determines how family relationships influence on the life of protagonists. Some key passages are given to illustrate the author's techniques in conveying childhood memories. Furthermore, it analyses the hero's aspiration to become an independent individual in society.

Keywords: character, endure difficulties, theme, author, protagonist.

Introduction. Creating protagonists in autobiographical works requires great skill from every writer. Through the way a writer depicts characters according to their imagination, readers can draw conclusions about what kind of people these literary characters are. By observing how characters behave in the development of a story's events, one can study their character traits. Heroes who endure difficulties and overcome challenging situations are considered the main driving force of the plot in a literary work.

The tradition of creating characters varies in world literature and characters are often classified as primary and secondary. Primary characters are the main figures who actively participate in the events of the story. Secondary characters have a smaller role in the development of the plot.

Methodology. The article uses *thematic analysis* recurring themes such as family relationships, personal growth, and childhood hardships. The study highlights the authors' life experiences and how he conveyed his experiences through literary techniques. Some key excerpts from the primary texts were selected to illustrate the psychological, moral, and emotional development of characters.

The writers who write autobiographical works describe how the main character steps into a new life. To illustrate, Gorky depicted how his protagonist's uncles struggled over property and his grandfather was forced to divide up his possessions, after which he took his wife and grandson and moved to a new house elsewhere in his novella "Childhood". From this point, a profound turning point occurs in Alexey's life. The protagonist began to make new friends. The activities of a close neighbor called "Khoroshoye Delo" ("Good Deed") attracted his attention:

"I became depressed; my heart was weighed down by some kind of vague unease. 'Khoroshoye Delo' deeply astonished me: I felt sorry for him, and his sunken eyes would not leave my mind." In his childhood memories, the writer depicted the landscape around the Volga River and, through it, conveyed the emotional experiences of Alyosha's inner world:

"The sun drifts almost imperceptibly over the Volga. Everything around changes and renews itself with every passing hour. The lush green hills resemble magnificent folds adorning the earth in its precious garment. The towns and villages along the river recall sweets arranged on a tray; golden-yellow autumn leaves float along the surface of the water."

Results and discussion. The novella "*Childhood*" by the Russian writer Maxim Gorky belongs to the genre of autobiographical novels, in which the author recalled events he experienced during his own childhood. Gorky's "*Childhood*" was written in 1913, and the story begins with the main character, Alexey, losing his father. The child still did not understand that he had lost his father; his childish mind could not yet grasp it. With his tender, immature heart, Alyosha did not fully realize that he was left without a father, and he would look now at his father's body, now at his mother's sorrowful face. The writer described the condition of his mother, who was plunged into grief after her husband's death, as follows:

"My mother crushed my heart; her tears and lamentations ignited some new, anxious feeling in my soul. It was the first time I had seen my mother in such a state; before that she always carried herself with great restraint, spoke calmly, kept her clothes spotless, her clean body was hard as stone, her hands extraordinarily strong – she was a solid, robust woman "Another dim memory that has remained with me is a rainy day, a secluded corner of the cemetery; I am standing and looking into the grave where my father's coffin has been placed, on a slippery mound of sticky, piled-up earth; at the bottom of the grave a good deal of water has collected, frogs can be seen there, and two of them have already climbed onto the bright yellow lid of the coffin. [4.5]" The main character, Alexey, described how he felt as he recalled his father's death, standing in a secluded corner of the cemetery on one of the rainy days:

In his childhood memories, the writer enriches his image of his grandmother with her positive qualities. He expresses his impressions through the voice of young Alyosha in

sincere words: “When my grandmother told a fairy tale, she never hurried. In a mysterious manner, leaning toward me, she would fix her sharp eyes on mine, and it seemed as though her widened pupils were giving strength to my heart, lifting my spirit. Her speech itself was like a song; the more she spoke, the smoother and more flowing her words sounded. Anyone who listens to her stories takes great pleasure in them. As I sit listening, I beg her: ‘Tell me more! [4.15]’”

In “Childhood”, certain features of the hero’s and the author’s childhood, as well as his psychological experiences, are vividly reflected in the following ways:

1. The ruthless struggles of his stone-hearted uncles over land and property, their coarseness, and especially the severe beating Alexey received for dyeing cloth without his grandfather’s permission, mark the beginning of the “most difficult days” of the protagonist’s life. From that moment on, he began to feel humiliation and suffering in his life:

“My grandfather beat me until I lost consciousness. After that, I lay ill for several days in a small one-windowed house, sunk into a wide, warm bed. In the corner of the main room there was a shelf with several icons, and a red lamp burned there day and night without going out. The days I spent sick in bed became the most important moments of my life. During that time, it seems I grew up considerably, for I sensed that something new had appeared within me. From those days on, a feeling of restless compassion toward people awakened in me, as if a veil had been torn from my heart, and my heart became indescribably sensitive – not only to my own pain and sorrow, but even to the suffering of others.” Alyosha would remember the beating he received from his grandfather for the rest of his life, and recalling that the person who had beaten him was his own grandfather always wounded the writer’s soul.

The stories his grandmother told were about his father and they had a very strong influence on the main character’s inner world. Hearing these stories, Alyosha began to form an image of what kind of person his father had been. The writer described the expression of anxiety on the protagonist’s face as follows:

“At night I do not sleep; through the bluish window I watch the stars slowly drifting across the sky. In my mind I invent all kinds of sorrowful events, and in these stories my father occupies an important place: holding a stick in his hand, with a shaggy dog at his side, he is always going somewhere alone. [4.272]”

2. The main character’s aspiration to become an independent individual in society. After his mother’s death, Alexey began to work in order to help his grandmother and to support himself. Through labor, he started to lead a free and independent life. When the protagonist began attending school, his sharp intellect and quick mind became evident. He recalls how happy he was after successfully completing the third grade, bringing his report card home:

“At last I passed the examinations and moved on to the third grade. As a reward, I received a Bible, a bound collection of Krylov’s fables, and another book without a cover, on which was written an incomprehensible word, ‘Fata Morgana.’ I was also given a certificate. When I brought the rewards home, my grandfather was overjoyed and excited; he said that all these things had to be carefully preserved, that he would put the books into his chest and lock them away. [4.326]”

Ch.Aytmatov presents to readers an artistic portrayal of the events he personally experienced, rendering the pure and simple years of his childhood in his autobiographical novella “*My Childhood*”. In particular, the writer emphasizes that during the period in which he lived, the war disrupted the lives of all people:

“In my work I always recall the Second World War. This war was not only for us, but for all of humanity, an extremely heavy and terrible loss, an unforgettable event. To say that this war brought death and famine to people would be to understate its devastation. That war also assaulted the morality and ethics of the people of that time, inflicting immeasurable harm on the customs, traditions, and rituals that had been formed over centuries. [5.200]”

After the war, thieves increased throughout the country and began to plunder the people. Among other things, even the cow that sustained the writer’s family from day to day was stolen: “I realized that a great calamity had befallen us. It was clear that the cow had been stolen. I ran toward the house to inform my mother. At that moment, the bright world turned into a dark night for us. There was no doubt that our livestock had been stolen. Hearing such chilling news before dawn, my mother and my younger brothers sat crying sadly, not knowing what to do. This unpleasant event put an end to our lives and it was a heavy tragedy. [5.149]”

Since Chingiz had become the sole provider of his family after his father, the responsibility of caring for his household fell entirely on him. That is why he suffered greatly when he could not find the missing cow and he wished to find the thief which would make him happy. Not knowing what to do, he would cry. His whole body would tremble as he searched every field, plain, and rocky hill without leaving a place unchecked. Despite the cold, he ran through the snow, wearing only the single boot he had: “At one point my boot came apart at the seams, and the short winter day was beginning to end. In this bright world, it seemed that only I existed; in this desolate land, there was no one in my situation. The surroundings were silent. Lifeless mountains stretched into the endless distance, and the flat plains without trees or shrubs gleamed as if alive. There was no trace of either the thief or the cow. No trace! No, no! No trace! There was nothing near or far!” [5.141]

The boy carried a rifle in his hand, determined to take revenge on the thief and shoot him as soon as he saw him. The writer entered the world called “literature” with the aim of

depicting the difficult moments he experienced. People, reading about his past, begin to vividly imagine the heavy trials of history.

Moreover, in Uzbek literature, “*Tales from the Past*” by Abdulla Qahhor portrays the author’s youth. The writer’s childhood years were spent in the villages of Yaypan, Nursuq, Qudash, Buvaydi, Oqqo‘rg‘on, Olqor, and Yulg‘unzor in the Fergana Valley. He described the events he witnessed with his own eyes and to portray scenes from past life.

Conclusion. It is known that autobiographical works show the personal experiences of authors by providing real life events of their lives. Thematic analysis reveals psychological, moral, and emotional development of characters. The ruthless struggles of the protagonist’s stone-hearted uncles over land and property, their coarseness, and especially the severe beating Alexey received for dyeing cloth without his grandfather’s permission, mark the beginning of the “most difficult days” of the protagonist’s life. Writers enrich their description by giving some evidences from their lives. They expressed their impressions through the language of their characters.

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